

From sawdust to mycelium for insulation and packaging

Sawdust can be used as a substrate to grow mycelium. Generally, mycelium has the potential to utilize any kind of substrate like logs, cardboard, straw and wood chips. Nevertheless, especially for side-and waste streams such as saw dust it creates new possibilities for meaningful applications. In line with the cradle-to-cradle idea, a growing number of bio pioneers experiment with mycelium. Particularly mycelium-based composites used for sound and thermal insulation have a very low carbon footprint compared to other materials used for these purposes. Next to this, mycelium grown from sawdust can be used as bio foams replacing polystyrene (EPS), which are normal lightweight crude-oil based packaging materials. Thereby, the utilization of sawdust as substrate to grow mycelium is not only a way to increase circularity of building and packaging materials but also to steer to a natural and fossil-free environment.

Regional coverage and transferability

Growing mycelium is a very old technique. Gourmet mushrooms, which can also be grown in a saw dust substrate, is basically practiced in any part of the world. In eastern Asian cultures such as Singapore also the tradition of fermented mushrooms, clearly belongs to the cultural heritage. However, the current movements of growing mycelium composites that can be used for packaging or insulation can hardly be located within Europe since many pioneers have started experimenting at the same time. For this reason, this good practice is not particularly bound to any region. Developments can be seen anywhere in the world. Growing mycelium in saw dust can be transferable in need of those characteristics.

Image: Heide Schmitz, Stephan Voth, Daniel Pfeifferer, "Spent mushroom substrate and sawdust to produce mycelium-based thermal insulation composites", *Journal of Cleaner Production* Vol. 313, 2021, 128168 (2021-07-20)

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ The utilization of saw dust as substrate to grow mycelium creates new business opportunities, which will lead to less saw dust that is burned or wasted without any useful application.
- ▶ The collection of saw dust from sawmills needs enhanced waste management operations.
- ▶ Bio pioneers experimenting with mycelium have initiated a very innovative movement leading to more and more co-creation.
- ▶ Resource efficiency is enhanced since the wooden materials are kept in use – not as wood but as a new evolution.
- ▶ Growing mycelium can be done causing basically nor harmful emissions. Next to the biowaste only small amounts of water are needed and just when the mycelium is there the organism is killed by heaters, which has only little climate impact.